

Divalent Cobalt, Copper and Zinc Complexes of *N*-Salicylideneamino Acids

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Complexes of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with *N*-salicylideneamino acids have been prepared. Amino acids used were glycine, L-alanine and L-phenylalanine. The Schiff bases function as terdentate with O, O and N donors from carboxylic, phenolic and imine groups respectively. An octahedral geometry around Co^{II} and Zn^{II} , and a square-planar geometry around Cu^{II} have been proposed.

Schiff bases have found wide applications in the field of coordination chemistry¹. Salicylaldehyde amino acid Schiff base complexes² have been used to model *N*-pyridoxylidene amino acids which are considered to be an important intermediate in biological amination process³. A perusal of the literature reveals that bivalent metal complexes with the above-mentioned ligands have not been studied in detail. Manganese(II)⁴ and oxovanadium(IV)⁵ complexes with imines derived from *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and few amino acids have been reported. This prompted us to synthesise Co^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes *in situ* with *N*-salicylideneamino acids.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) were stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, insoluble in water and many common organic solvents. The molar conductance values of 10^{-3} M solutions of the complexes in dry DMF lie in the range $5\text{--}13 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, indicating their non-electrolytic nature⁶.

In ir spectra of the 1 : 1 complexes, coordinated water molecules showed a broad band at $3400\text{--}3300 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (OH). Presence of imine structure is indicated by the band around 1630cm^{-1} (N=CH) appearing in all the complexes. $\Delta\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ was consistently observed to be greater than 200cm^{-1} [$\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO}^-) \sim 1600$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-) \sim 1400 \text{cm}^{-1}$] which indicated unidenticity of carboxylate group⁷. Band at $1540\text{--}1525 \text{cm}^{-1}$ for all the complexes can be attributed to phenolic C–O stretching⁸. In the 1 : 2 complexes, a broad band around 3400cm^{-1} indicates the coordination of phenolic OH group without loss of hydrogen. Bonding of phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms can be corroborated by the appearance of $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ vibrations⁹ at $520\text{--}480$ and $440\text{--}400 \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively, for all the complexes.

Electronic spectra of all the complexes possess a high energy absorption band with maxima at $\sim 260 \text{nm}$ which can be assigned to benzenoid $\pi\text{--}\pi^*$ transition. At low energies, metal complexes exhibit a band at $\sim 350 \text{nm}$ which is indicative of $\pi\text{--}\pi^*$ transition originating mainly in the aldimine residue¹⁰.

Cobalt(II) complexes showed bands at $8000\text{--}10000$ and $18000\text{--}21000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ for transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3). $\text{Co}(\text{sal-gly})_2$ exhibited two bands at 9185 and 19236cm^{-1} , suggesting octahedral geometry¹². These bands were observed in case of $\text{Co}(\text{sal-L-ala})_2$ at 8440 and 19900cm^{-1} respectively. The effective magnetic moment values (Table 1) were found to be within the range $4.30\text{--}5.20$ B.M. as expected for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹².

The diffused reflectance spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showing a band around 16000cm^{-1} [in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{sal-L-phen})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 15847cm^{-1}] is assigned to the transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ and is characteristic of square-planar geometry^{11,13}. The band often exhibits a broad tail into the near-ir region [in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{sal-L-phen})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 5220cm^{-1}]. The magnetic moment values are within the expected range ($1.70\text{--}2.20$ B.M.) for d^9 -system¹². Zinc(II) complexes are diamagnetic as expected for d^{10} -configuration.

¹H nmr spectra were recorded only for Zn^{II} complexes because their TFA solutions were clear unlike other metal

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis (%) :		Λ_M	μ_{eff} B.M.
	Found	(Calcd.)		
	M	N		
$[\text{Co}(\text{sal-gly})_2]$	13.92	6.50	8.3	4.85
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3)_2$	(14.20)	(6.75)		
$[\text{Co}(\text{sal-L-ala})_2]$	13.11	6.24	8.2	4.87
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_3)_2$	(13.30)	(6.32)		
$[\text{Co}(\text{sal-L-phen})\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15.25	3.29	5.0	4.66
$\text{Co}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_3)\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(15.51)	(3.68)		
$[\text{Cu}(\text{sal-gly})\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	24.32	5.28	5.5	1.74
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{NO}_3)\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	(24.57)	(5.41)		
$[\text{Cu}(\text{sal-L-ala})\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	23.13	5.15	12.4	1.85
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3)\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	(23.31)	(5.13)		
$[\text{Cu}(\text{sal-L-phen})\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18.03	3.88	9.1	1.90
$\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_3)\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	(18.23)	(4.01)		
$[\text{Zn}(\text{sal-gly})\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	21.85	4.55	8.4	dia
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{NO}_3)\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(22.05)	(4.72)		
$[\text{Zn}(\text{sal-L-ala})\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	20.91	4.61	13.0	dia
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3)\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(21.06)	(4.51)		
$[\text{Zn}(\text{sal-L-phen})\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16.67	3.44	12.9	dia
$\text{Zn}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_3)\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	(16.91)	(3.62)		

complexes. The azomethine proton signal for these complexes at δ 8.15–8.30 indicates the presence of imine structure. Other signals observed are as follows: [Zn(sal-gly).3H₂O] δ (TFA) 4.50 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.70–7.51 (4H, m, ArH); [Zn(Sal-L-ala).3H₂O] δ (DMSO-d₆) 1.42 (3H, d, CH₃), 2.50 (1H, q, α -CH), 6.80–7.70 (4H, m, ArH); [Zn(sal-L-phen).3H₂O] δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.15 (2H, d, CH₂), 3.90 (1H, m, α -CH), 6.21–7.20 (9H, m, ArH).

The insolubility of the complexes in water and common organic solvents and their infusibility at higher temperature indicate polymeric nature.

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents were used of AnalaR grade. Salicylaldehyde (Sarabhai M. Chemicals) and amino acids (Loba-Chemie) and metal acetates (Albright and Wilson) were used. Metal contents were estimated using standard methods¹⁴.

Synthesis of the complexes: Aqueous solution of sodium salt of amino acid was stirred with hot ethanolic solution of the aldehyde in equimolar ratio for about 30 min. The aqueous ethanolic solution of metal acetates of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were added to hot ligand solution in 1:1, 1:2 and 1: excess molar ratios. The reactants were stirred for about 15 h. The resulting solid products were successively washed with water-ethanol and diethyl ether, and dried *in vacuo* over P₂O₅. The purity was checked by tlc. The yields of the complexes varied from 80 to 90%.

Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 842 spectrophotometer, diffused reflectance spectra on a Carry 2390 spectrophotometer (at RSIC, IIT, Madras) and ¹H nmr spectra on a 90 MHz Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Conductivity was measured on an Elico CM82T conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was determined at room temperature (25 ± 3°) using a vibrating sample magnetometer 155 at USIC, University of Roorkee, Roorkee.

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